

“RHETORICAL ABILITY”: REASON, EMOTION, AND CHARACTER AS HEURISTICS FOR THE EVALUATION OF EFFICACY IN DESIGN

G. Mauricio Mejía
University of Caldas, Colombia
✉ mauricio.mejiaramirez@ucaldas.edu.co

Sauman Chu
University of Minnesota, USA
✉ schu@umn.edu

ABSTRACT

Usability inspection is a major standard for design evaluation in which expert evaluators use heuristics to assess efficiency and quality. However, usability alone is insufficient to assess efficacy in design problems in which the main design goal is not cognitive interaction. For example, goals such as social change (e.g. health promotion), communication, or entertainment, in the field of product and system design, require design evaluation that goes beyond usability. In this paper we argue that rhetorical ability (or *rhetorability*) is a plausible heuristic evaluation approach in the field of design for social change. We propose nine heuristics based on the three rhetorical appeals, logos (reason), pathos (emotion), and ethos (credibility). The applicability of the method depends on the understanding of the rhetorical situation; thus, the rhetorical ability heuristic evaluator should be an expert in the audience needs, the design goal, and the design problem.

KEYWORDS: *design evaluation, expert evaluation, rhetorical ability, rhetorical appeals, design efficacy, design for social change.*

INTRODUCTION

The expert evaluation of a design outcome (image, product, service, or system) may be carried out from different perspectives depending on the evaluation goal. One perspective is ease or efficiency of use; another is efficacy of the goal. Usability inspection is a type of expert evaluation for finding usability problems in interactive products (Nielsen, 1994). It focuses on efficiency and has become a major standard for several reasons. First, the introduction of digital interactive systems with complex human-machine interactions generated a need for evaluation methods and design principles capable of helping designers reduce cognitive friction for users (see Cooper, Reiman, & Cronin, 2007). Second, experts are able to carry out a rapid assessment with relatively simple observations. Further, usability can be used as a tool to indirectly argue other benefits such as visits and usage.

Another perspective is efficacy in terms of the design goal. To directly assess efficacy in design goals such as increased sales, political persuasion, or social change, usability can provide insights into people's ability to employed or interact with the design outcome. However, it is insufficient to assess goal efficacy. General expert evaluation methods can be used to assess efficacy in design, but there are no heuristics to

guide the assessment process. We propose using heuristics based on the theory of rhetoric to assess the efficacy of design outcomes, with a focus on design for social change. We call this heuristics rhetorical ability or *rhetorability*.

THEORY OF RHETORIC FOR DESIGN EVALUATION

Aristotle wrote his *Rhetoric* more than two thousand years ago. By his time, rhetoric was understood as a persuasive art for public speaking in political debate, courts and public events in a context of Greece's emerging democracy. Today, rhetorical theory has been used in different fields to study varied social phenomena. Buchanan has reviewed rhetoric with a view to theorizing the design field, arguing that rhetoric was one of the first design activities (Buchanan, 1995). According to Schriver (1997), the preoccupation with the audience and context in the Russian constructivist or German Bauhaus design movements initiated the rhetorical approach to design.

In practical terms relevant to the field of design, rhetoric is a method that serves both for the analysis and production of design outcomes (Bonsiepe, 2000; Buchanan, 1985). Since rhetoric can be used for analysis, it also has a particular

potential to be used in evaluation. In the modern theory of rhetoric in design, it has been proposed that the diverse rhetorical components might be used to understand the design activity. For example, in classic rhetoric there are five canons or divisions for the speech creation process: invention (finding arguments), arrangement or disposition (ordering arguments), style (form of expression), memory, and delivery or action. These canons are a model that can be used to define five phases for design production (Ehse, 1984) or to organize designers' abilities and their correspondence to design specialties (Buchanan, 1995).

The component of rhetoric that is best suited to analyze and assess the characteristics of design outcomes is rhetorical appeals (Mejía & Chu, 2014). According to Aristotle rhetorical appeals or modes of persuasion are: the truth or apparent truth of the arguments (logos), leading the audience to feel emotions (pathos), and the credibility of the spoken word (ethos) (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). In simple terms, logos refers to appeals to reason, pathos appeals to emotion, and ethos appeals to credibility. As is the case for any speech, design consists of a persuasive argument that has recourse to the three appeals. The division between them is an artificial theoretical concept for analysis.

Aristotle explained that when there are not enough facts or evidence, rhetorical production can help make decisions (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Alternatively, when the facts and evidence are insufficient to change social behaviors, rhetorical appeals can arguably constitute a powerful tool. For example, there is strong evidence to suggest that poor diets and lack of exercise cause obesity, but merely communicating this evidence is not enough to change health behaviors. Removing premises in order to generate logos appeals or incorporating pathos and ethos indices may be more effective in bringing about change. Furthermore, the challenge is greater with low-skilled low-literacy audiences. The rhetorician-designer seeks to create effective speech-designs that aid social change, using rhetorical appeals rather than evidence to help people take action in the desired direction.

Braet (1992) provided a useful reflection regarding the argumentative nature of the three rhetorical appeals. He reviewed them in Aristotle's work, seeking to assess if pathos and ethos could be considered enthymemes (arguments). He first demonstrated that the logos appeal is the central enthymeme of a speech. He then explained that the pathos and ethos appeals could have two uses: one as indices shown (interpreted by the audience) and one as arguments proven (presented by the speaker). He explained that using pathos or ethos as enthymemes may counter the persuasion goal. For example, "attempting to prove ethos would produce doubt about the ethos! Only when one is certain that the ethos has been undermined by prejudices, can proving the ethos make sense" (p. 312). Also, enthymematic pathos could reduce the strength of the emotion, or be useless. Braet concluded that in an effective speech, logos enthymeme or argument might be combined with ethos and/or pathos indices. Adapting Braet's interpretation to the field of design means that logos

is the base appeal in design outcomes, to which pathos and ethos indices may be added to a greater or lesser degree.

DESIGN RESEARCH ON RHETORICAL APPEALS

Rhetorical appeals have been used distinctively as tools for analysis of design outcomes and as research variables. In a theoretical essay, Buchanan (1985), analyzed the rhetorical appeals of industrial design products like spoons, coffee mills, and lamps in a discussion about the need to create more intelligible products and to enhance the ways in which designers communicate with their audiences. He argued that logos refers to how designers propose a technological reasoning and practical functions for objects, how pathos refers to the ways in which designers put users in emotional states to generate desire and satisfaction, and how ethos refers to the ways they gain credibility by showing concern for the audience and creating confidence about the use of objects.

A different application of rhetoric in design is the practical framework for graphic design production developed by Ehse (2008). He described the application of concepts of rhetoric such as rhetorical situation and rhetorical canons, but placed particular emphasis on rhetorical appeals and rhetorical figures. He argued that there are logos-driven graphic design products such as wayfinding design or instructional documents, pathos-driven products such as advertisements and ethos-driven products such as social and health topics. He also operationalized rhetorical appeals strategies; for logos: the organization of information, choice of fonts, hierarchy, and consistency with the goal of facilitating understanding; for pathos: special arrangements, visual symbolism, and choice of images and colors with the goal of triggering emotions; while for ethos the strategy is a simple translation from rhetoric: employing a general conceptual approach in order to provide credibility, empathy, and reliability. These strategies are limited to visual composition elements. Van der Waarde (2010) used Ehse's rhetorical framework as a reference for an analysis of communication in European medical pamphlets, discussing the rhetorical situation, canons, and appeals. He argued that the components of rhetoric served as tools to explain failures in communication standards.

Recently, one of the authors of this paper was involved in two studies, one of which used rhetorical appeals to conduct an analysis of viral videos for social change (Mejía & Longo, 2012). The authors interviewed experts and analyzed the rhetorical appeals in four videos including *The Story of Stuff* (The Story of Stuff Project, 2007) - an animation presented by Annie Leonard about the negative environmental effects of the production and consumption of industrial goods and *RSA Animate - The Crisis of Capitalism* (Royal Society for the Encouragement of Arts, Manufactures, and Commerce, RSA, 2010) - a lecture by David Harvey animated with real-time drawings that explains the oppressive effects of capitalism and claims the need for action. They identified salient indices of appeals

to logos, pathos, and ethos. After publication these salient indices were reviewed and refined:

Logos

- Simplicity (of content and use of redundant visual elements)
- Simple rational metaphors (using color or shape)
- Audio-visual consistency (or synchrony between audio and visual information)
- Appropriate symbols (for the audience)
- Rational narrative style (such as documentary or lecture)
- Use of evidence (such as facts or historical information)
- Directions of action (to be taken for social change)

Pathos

- Emotional elements (that are playful, positive, or aggressive such as humor, hope, or danger)
- Ethical content (such as claims of corruption, irresponsibility or greed to elicit emotional reactions)
- Reception comfort (such as a sense of calm or urgency generated in the audience)
- Audience sensitive content (such as disturbing content)

Ethos

- Neutrality (information appears to be objective or biased)
- Visual style is empathetic (with the experiences of the audience)
- Narrator appearance (in coherence with the message)
- Narrator profile (in coherence with the message)
- Narrator tone (in coherence with the message)
- Supporting organization (increases reputation of the message)

In the second study, Mejía explored and evaluated rhetorical appeal strategies used in design for social change; specifically an interactive product for obesity prevention targeted at Latinos (Mejía, 2013). The study explored rhetorical appeals, designing a mobile web application with three versions, or modes, each using different rhetorical appeal strategies. The infographic mode focused on logos and had a reduced number of pathos and ethos indices, the comic mode had increased pathos indices and the realistic mode had increased ethos indices. The data was collected using auto-observation during the design process, which was examined by design experts using rhetorical appeal heuristics and through qualitative interviews in a real world context. The author, the external design experts and the audience had different perceptions regarding the rhetorical appeals. In the design process, the author had initially planned different rhetorical strategies but in the end concluded that they were similar. The design experts found significant differences, while the users interviewed did not perceive any. The study concluded that de-

signers lend their attention to visual and textual elements and overlook the influence of the design concept, format, and interactivity on the rhetorical appeals.

Building on this existing research, the following section of this paper presents the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics. Admittedly, grounded evidence directly related to the design of rhetorical appeals is limited; nonetheless, rhetorical theory shows great promise both for the production and the evaluation of persuasive design intended to change people's behaviors.

RHETORICAL ABILITY HEURISTICS

This section discusses concepts of rhetorical appeal and proposes heuristics for evaluating design using the findings of research into rhetorical appeals found in the design research literature.

Logos – reason

Aristotle explained that logos is the logical argument presented either in the form of enthymemes or paradigms. Enthymemes are incomplete syllogisms in which a reason is provided alongside a conclusion (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). For example the syllogism “he is healthy because he eats vegetables” is an enthymeme; the complete syllogism would be “People who eat vegetables are healthy. He eats vegetables. Therefore, he is healthy”. Paradigms are inductions that consist of stating a particular observation and leaving the conclusion unstated (Aristotle & Kennedy). For example, “he became healthier eating more vegetables” is a paradigm. Design strategies or characteristics are difficult to identify as enthymemes or paradigms unless there is explicit verbal content that takes those forms. Consequently, rational elements or strategies that induce rational/logical thinking or facilitate cognitive processing are identified as appeals to logos. Points 1. to 3., below, describe the rhetorical ability heuristics we propose that are associated with appeals to reason:

1. *Perceptual information and interactive structure facilitate cognitive processing.*

At the level of visual composition, this heuristic encompasses Eshes' (2008) logos strategies to facilitate understanding (organization of information, choice of fonts, hierarchy, and consistency). Depending on the media employed, interactive structures such as audio-visual consistency in videos (Mejía & Longo, 2012) may become relevant. This heuristic is related to general usability heuristics proposed by Nielsen (Nielsen, 1995). However, rational persuasion is not the same as usable and human-centered design. The design must strategically provide information and interaction to help people change their knowledge, attitudes, or behaviors. The perceptual information and interactive structures are adequate in quantity and level of complexity according to the rhetorical situation. While some situations may require large amounts

of information and high complexity in information and interaction (e.g. asking medical doctors to change medical procedures), other situations may require limited information and low complexity (e.g. asking poor people to increase their savings). In general, the information presented and the interaction options should help people to reason. This demands that the designer should decide about the adequate “dosage”, or quantity, of information and the complexity of the experience. In social change goals, presenting limited information might help to nudge people towards adopting desired behaviors.

2. *Level of abstraction matches the audience's skills and culture*

High abstraction that is adequate for high-skill high-literacy people is not always the best design solution. Generally, for low-skill low-literacy audiences or people from a particular culture, low abstraction (or high iconicity) would help to understand directions or messages. Krampen (1965) suggested that graphic symbols could be used in developing countries to help communicate information among audiences with low literacy. He argued that, for these countries, design should consist of simple and realistic graphic symbols because the use of style or attractive expression may confuse the audience. Also, Latino parents in an underserved community showed preference for realistic illustrations of children over infographic-like abstractions to represent levels of obesity in a logical way (Mejía, 2013). Furthermore, people from specific cultures may not understand some very abstracted symbols that are designed for ideal universal audiences, such as AIGA symbols for men's and women's restrooms. The exception to this rule is the use of cultural symbols that are highly abstracted yet easy to understand because people are familiar with them.

3. *Logical explanations are provided, preferably within the duration of the interaction routine.*

In the audiovisual medium this could be controlled, because all information is processed during the interaction. The salient indices of rational narrative style and use of evidence in viral videos developed by Mejía and Longo (2012) illustrate this. However, in other design outcomes such as interactive websites, industrial products, or services, logical explanations are not provided in the interaction routine. A classic problem in industrial products is people trying to use products without reading the accompanying manuals, either because they are not willing to make the effort or because the manual is for some reason not at hand. Van der Waarde (2010) described another example, explaining that information in medical pamphlets follows a logical order required by the relevant European Directive. He argued that the overwhelming list of side effects compared to the short description of benefits hinders patients' ability to make rational decisions. Additionally, whereas the likelihood of side effects is provided, the probability of effectiveness is not. This is an example of a lack of logical explanation and an exaggerated exten-

sion of explanation for the interaction routine, which illustrates a cause of failure to persuade people to take their medicines.

Pathos – emotion

Aristotle explained that leading the audience to feel certain emotions of pleasure or pain is an appeal to pathos. These emotions are temporary states of mind and affect audience judgment. According to Aristotle the emotions pathos opposes are anger/calmness, friendliness/hostility, fear/confidence, shame/shamelessness, kindness/unkindness, pity/indignation, and envy/emulation. The positive or negative emotion is used depending on the rhetorical situation (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Pathos heuristics consist of applying Aristotle's description directly: does the design outcome lead the audience to feel the adequate emotions? Points 4. to 6., below, constitute a list of the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics related to appeals to emotion:

4. *People are driven to aesthetically enjoy, explore, or endure the design.*

At the level of visual composition, this heuristic is related to Ehses' (2008) pathos strategies, which are themselves associated with aesthetic elements (special arrangements, image and color choice). Nielsen's recommendation of minimalist aesthetics (Nielsen, 1995) is only suitable if it is the best strategy in a particular rhetorical situation. In the majority of situations other aesthetics that elicit positive or negative emotions would be more persuasive. For example, some designs require complex narrative structures or experiences if they are to generate emotional engagement. In a mobile web application designed by the author to promote healthy behaviors (Mejía, 2013), Latino parents showed a strong preference for comic and realistic graphic styles rather than abstracted infographics. This engagement creates an affective response that aids behavior change.

5. *Emotional comfort or friction is generated as a function of the goals.*

There is a tendency to associate pleasurable comfortable emotions with successful design. According to Buchanan (1985), emotional persuasion occurs in the interaction with the object or its contemplation, which should be experienced as fulfilling experiences. For Van der Waarde (2010), in his work on medical pamphlets, pathos-persuasive information should put the patient in the right emotional state of mind, something that European medical information does not do because the relevant European Directive restricts promotional messages, and the experience of opening a pack and unfolding the pamphlets, which contain a large amount of information, is intimidating. Nonetheless, painful emotions that cause emotional friction may be required to achieve the design goals, particularly in social change. For example, some social change viral videos have used sensitive content such as showing how chemical substances may

have reached the milk in the breasts of nursing mothers in order to explain the effects of climate change (Mejía & Longo, 2012). Mejía made use of emotions of shame in gestures made by obese children as a pathos strategy to counter the belief of Latino parents that a healthy child should be chubby (Mejía, 2013).

6. *Symbolism matches audience's culture*

Some symbols are able to carry cultural meanings that generate particular emotional reactions and, hence, may be utilized in design to lead audience to feel desired emotions. According to Aristotle, speakers try to arouse positive or negative emotions in the audience, depending on the rhetorical situation (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). The meanings aroused by symbols should be part of the culture, allowing people to make the correct interpretations and, therefore, experience the right emotions. For example, one of the viral videos analyzed by the authors (Mejía & Longo, 2012) used a theme taken from the game of *Monopoly* to visualize a lecture about capitalism. The designer used this theme knowing that the audience was familiar with the symbolism employed and was able to understand it correctly as a metaphor. Another example is the classic use of national symbols that are associated with patriotic attitudes in order to generate emotional effects.

Ethos – credibility

In Aristotle, ethos refers to the credibility of the speaker - not based on his or her reputation but created in the delivery of the speech. The audience projects a profile of the speaker as a preparation for making a judgment. Wisdom (practical sense), virtue (ability to verbalise thoughts), and good will (prudence and fair-mindedness) are the three ethos reasons (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Since in design the speaker is assumed to be the manufacturer, sponsor, or service provider - that is, an entity that is not dynamically “delivering” the design - reputation is a core part of the ethos appeal. Buchanan also emphasized that design products that appeal to ethos are those that show concern and “speak in familiar voices” (Buchanan, 1985, p. 15). Empathic design that understands the feelings and needs of the audience generates credibility appeals. Points 7. to 9., below, constitute a list of the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics related to appeals to emotion:

7. *The reputation of the manufacturer, sponsor, or service provider is visible and clear.*

When clearly apparent in the interaction experience the reputation of the organization or designer will affect the credibility appeal. Van der Waarde's (2010) analysis recognizes this; he concluded that the nature of these medical information texts is ambiguous because patients are not able to distinguish clearly whether the information comes from the pharmaceutical industry, the doctor, the pharmacist, or the regulators. This confusion reduces the credibility of the information. In another example, Mejía used a university logo and technical medical language to strengthen the credibility of a health communication

for Latinos (Mejía, 2013), finding that this information appealed to the ethos of the audience, preparing them to assimilate the information.

8. *The design outcome appears to profoundly understand audience feelings and needs (empathy)*

This is a challenging characteristic for design and evaluation. Design practitioners and evaluators will probably need to know if they are to be able to achieve empathy or be able to assess it. Participatory design, or other qualitative methods should help in this. In one of the viral videos analyzed by Mejía and Longo (2012), for instance, the presenter describes her personal experience with consumer products and lifestyles, which match many feelings in the audience, in order to gain credibility. Recently, Mejía included personal stories of children's characters in a mobile web application hoping to generate higher emotional engagement. He subsequently found during participant interviews that the stories matched stories that were already familiar to participants, which gave high degrees of credibility to the design product (Mejía, 2013). In these examples, empathy was achieved and successfully motivated behavior change.

9. *Neutrality or bias match audience expectations*

In Western audiences where science has a respected status the use of facts or evidence is associated with credibility. This information is considered neutral and the audience considers it to be credible. In political debates biased positions may be expected; for instance, in a right wing party, biased conservative discourses will gain credibility. Mejía and Longo also observed this characteristic in viral videos in which a neutral or biased narrator profile, appearance, and tone are critical for credibility (Mejía & Longo, 2012). For example, in the Story of Stuff video (The Story of Stuff Project, 2007), the presenter uses a calm and neutral tone to explain climate issues and encourage behavior change. This was a successful strategy because the video is not perceived to have a liberal bias.

CONCLUSION

We have developed and explained a list of nine heuristics for use in rhetorical ability evaluation, which are supported by previous design research. The heuristics was developed by paying special attention to the efficacy of design for social change. To correctly use these heuristics, designers and evaluators must have a clear and deep understanding of the rhetorical situation. That is: audience characteristics, context, and the design goal. This understanding will permit the rhetorical ability of a design outcome to be assessed. Thus, the best expert is not an expert in design or rhetoric but rather an expert in the rhetorical situation of the design problem. The main challenge for the expert is to assess whether the design arguments and indices are adequate to the rhetorical situation. To ensure this the expert must note that sometimes

certain “rhetoric-able” outcomes must purposefully hinder cognitive processing (logos) or cause neutrality-bias dissonance (ethos) if they are to be successful in a particular rhetorical situation.

Furthermore, the nine heuristics are not exclusive to logos, pathos, or ethos. Depending on the rhetorical situation, a pathos heuristic may serve to assess logos appeals and so on. For instance, a symbol that does not match audience culture will not only fail to lead the audience to feel the expected emotion (pathos) but will also hinder rational cognitive processing (logos).

This list of heuristics will be tested in our future research agenda with the purpose of developing a specific rhetorical-ability protocol. Such a tool should include recommendations that aid understanding of the rhetorical situation of the design problem and appropriate definitions of the corresponding rhetorical appeal indices.

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